

Decentralization reform in Ukraine: main directions and priorities

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Abstract. In this article the author aims to analyze the essence of the legal bases of decentralization reform in Ukraine on the basis of conceptualization of theoretical principles and determination of priority directions of decentralization of power. The author notes that decentralization is one of the priority principles of the organization and functioning of public power and acts as a strategically determined vector of modern state policy; it is one of the components of almost all sectoral reforms. The article emphasizes that decentralization issues attract the attention of researchers from completely different scientific fields. However, either in theory or in practice there is no single unified concept of decentralization and its individual components, types, models. In the study the author came to the conclusion that, despite the multidimensionality of the concept of decentralization, the breadth of classification of its types, forms, models, the essence and content of this process should, above all, put two main aspects. First, the separation of powers and responsibilities between central, regional and local government, and second, the empowerment of citizens to address political, economic and social problems. Analyzing the basic approaches to decentralization, the author made the following conclusions: the state can carry out decentralization of power in the interests of the population, on the basis of law, transferring part of the powers of executive bodies to local self-government bodies; decentralization of powers must take into account the principle of subsidiarity.

Decentralization is one of the priority principles for the organization and functioning of public authority. In addition, it is a strategically determined vector of modern state policy; is one of the components of almost all sectoral reforms. The issue of decentralization has attracted the attention of researchers from completely different scientific fields. However, neither in theory nor in practice there is no single unified concept of decentralization and its individual components, types, models. According to foreign experts on this issue, the choice of form and accents of decentralization is a matter of defining the national strategy of relations between public authorities and management at all levels of territorial structure.

In the current context, decentralization is one of the factors of political security, which today becomes more acute and debatable. In any case, the priority and strategic importance of the principle of decentralization in public policy, both internationally and domestically, are obvious. This is evidenced by the provisions of the key documents of institutional and legal support for the modern state policy of Ukraine, first of all, the Association Agreement between Ukraine, on one hand, and the European Union, the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, on the other hand, the Sustainable Development Strategy Ukraine 2020, Coalition Agreement, Extraordinary Message from the President of Ukraine to the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine "On the Internal and External Situation of Ukraine, the Program of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. These documents reinforce the intention of the state and the desire of the society to modernize the public administration system and bring all its components in line with international legal standards.

Changing the governance model in Ukraine, with a clear focus on enhancing the role of local self-government in the development of territories of regions, and therefore the state, implies changes in the financial sphere and the administrative and territorial structure of the state. The main purpose of these reforms is to create capable local administrative and territorial units capable of effectively exercising local self-government, expanding their economic potential to fulfill their functions, as well as "educating" and strengthening local democracy.

In the first phase of the reform, through the instruments of decentralization of power, the separation of powers between state authorities and local self-government bodies has already begun, strengthening the financial capacity of regional self-government bodies and increasing the accountability of local authorities to communities. At present, some elements of administrative-territorial reform have been introduced, mechanisms for voluntary association of territorial communities have been activated, opportunities for

cooperation of territorial communities have been created, budget decentralization reform has been launched, and so on.

A functionally new political model should provide a more balanced mechanism of public administration and regional development, and create opportunities for completing the reform of the administrative and territorial structure of Ukraine. Economic initiatives for regional development should become one of the most important components of state policy for economic reform. Therefore, self-government bodies will carry out a whole range of measures that will stimulate the economic development of the territories: from state support of existing types of business to promotion of fundamentally new types of economic activity in the production and services sector.

The following scientists have devoted their problems to reforming local self-government and territorial organization of government in Ukraine, as well as to strengthening the financial base of local self-government bodies of the united territorial communities: V. Averianov, V. Kampo, Yu. Shemshuchenko, R. Bezsmertnyi, M. Dolishnii, P. Zhuk, Kh. Prykhodko, I. Storonianska, V. Kravtsiv, Yu. Bytiak, A. Tkachuk, A. Pelekhatyi. However, the current challenges of reforming local self-government and financial decentralization in Ukraine necessitate an in-depth study of the practical aspects of forming capable territorial communities. In the conditions of decentralization of the public finance system and implementation of the administrative-territorial reform in Ukraine, the outlined direction of the research has considerable potential.

The study focuses on public relations in the field of decentralization reform. The subject is scientific and theoretical developments, legal framework and legal principles of decentralization of power in Ukraine.

The author aims to analyze the essence of the legal foundations of decentralization reform in Ukraine on the basis of conceptualization of theoretical principles and determination of priority directions of decentralization of power.

The principle of decentralization as one of the priority principles of organization and functioning of public power, which is dictated by time and international experience, political maturity of Ukrainian society and obligations of Ukraine, becomes of utmost urgency and strategic importance in public policy. Having ratified the Association Agreement between Ukraine, on one hand, and the European Union, the European Atomic Energy Community and their member states, on the other hand, Ukraine has thus obtained a benchmark for its transformations, which are reflected in the key documents of modern state policy of Ukraine. First of all, the Sustainable Development Strategy "Ukraine 2020" [1] envisages the state's intention to modernize the public administration system and bring all its components in line with international legal standards.

In addition, decentralization serves not only as a strategically determined vector of modern state policy, but is one of the components of almost all sectoral reforms. Therefore, it is a prerequisite for the modernization of public administration, the social development of regions, an important factor in the successful implementation of which is a clear understanding of the essence, models and principles of decentralization of power and governance, which actualizes the topic of this research [2, 79].

Decentralization is a way of territorial organization of power in which the state transfers the right to make decisions on certain issues or in a certain sphere to structures of local or regional level, which are not part of the executive power system and are relatively independent from it. Decentralization is often understood as a redistribution of powers and competences between the central and local levels of public authority organization, with a shift in focus to the local level in terms of the implementation of functions defined in advance and guaranteed by the state [3, 7]. In general, it is a complex and multidimensional concept, so there are different interpretations of it.

Generalizations of theoretical achievements of foreign and domestic specialists in this field of knowledge [4, 19] give a good reason to argue that decentralization is a way of organizing public power, such a system of government, under which the state transfers the right to make decisions on certain issues or in a particular field local or regional level structures; it is a way of defining and differentiating tasks and functions, redistributing powers and levels of competence between different levels of government, most of which are transferred from the level of central government to the level of the lower and become their own task and powers.

At the same time, considering that "local affairs management can be exercised by both top-down officials of the state apparatus operating on the ground (local government) and on the basis of self-government of the population of administrative territorial units (local self-government)" [4, 20], some scholars consider the decentralization as the expansion and strengthening of the rights of territorial communities to independently resolve issues of local importance and to carry out their tasks within the limits established by law and under the responsibility of bodies and officials [5, 113], the granting of a wider range of powers and management functions to bodies that are not part of the executive power system and are relatively independent of it [6, 167], in fact local governments [7, 6], others adhere to the view that decentralization implies the extension of the competence of local administrative bodies, the transfer of powers and responsibilities for the exercise of state functions from the central government to the subordinate bodies of the local level [2, 79].

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Therefore, there is an opinion in the scientific literature about the existence of two types of decentralization: administrative (bureaucratic), which means the extension of the competence of local administrative bodies, which are entitled to independent activity against the central government, though appointed by the central government, and democratic, which implies the creation of an overblown system of local self-government in which the resolution of local affairs rests not on the representatives of the central government but on persons elected by the population of the relevant communities or regions [5, 7].

It is known that decentralization is defined as one of the key principles of democracy development in the Member States of the European Union (hereinafter - the EU) and the Council of Europe (hereinafter the CoE), the basis of their regional policy, along with the principles of subsidiarity, concentration, complementarity, partnership, programmatic approach. This principle is enshrined in the European Charter of Local Self-Government, the Draft European Charter for Regional Democracy, which refers to the redistribution of powers to regions in order to effectively use internal potential, to promote regional initiatives and to differentiate functions and powers between different levels of authorities [8].

Decentralization is a prerequisite for EU candidate countries and is based on all sectoral policies that are developed and implemented within the EU. In the 1996 Constitution, decentralization is associated not with the state executive power, but with the state power in general, the territorial aspect of its implementation (Articles 1, 2, 5, 7, 132). When carrying out decentralization, it is necessary to distinguish the levels of public authorities - central and local, intermediate regional. Each is characterized by the area of exclusive authority and competence, a system of guarantees against unauthorized interference of other levels in the legitimate implementation of this sphere. Among the subjects of decentralization of power there are people, state bodies, local and regional authorities, territorial communities of cities, towns, villages, and others. The practice of foreign countries shows that the model of their relationship should be based on the principles of decentralization, partnership and concerted action, regardless of the form of government [9]. The consideration of the subjects of decentralization is related to its objects - the statutory scope of powers and competencies of the respective state authorities. Components of this process are also the responsibility of public authorities, harmonization of actions of the subjects of power relations, availability of appropriate guarantees of their activity [10].

The issue of decentralization has attracted the attention of researchers from completely different scientific fields. However, either in theory or in practice there is no single unified (universal) concept of decentralization and its individual components, types, models. As foreign experts in this field point out, the choice of form and accents of decentralization is a matter of defining a national strategy of relations between public authorities and management at all levels of the territorial system. In the current context, decentralization is one of the factors of political security, which today becomes more acute and debatable. In any case, the priority and strategic importance of the principle of decentralization in public policy - both internationally and domestically - are obvious [11, 74].

In its turn, the study of the dynamics of political and legal reforms in different countries shows that the experience of each of them is peculiar, which should not be copied, but adapted according to the conditions and traditions of a particular society. Based on the analysis of foreign experience, it is possible to identify the main directions and priorities of implementing the relevant reforms in order to decentralize power in Ukraine:

- creation of conditions for efficient, coordinated and responsible activity of all branches of government, separation of powers and balancing of responsibilities of different levels of government, and limitation of interference in those areas where it is inappropriate;
- existence of special bodies of authority, first of all executive and / or in the system of local self-government, which would provide citizens with quality and accessible services (local and regional ombudsmen, municipal police, etc.);
- implementation of effective regional policy, state policy in the field of local self-government, which would ensure uniformity of local and regional development;
- development of the institution of regional self-government, giving it effective mechanisms of functioning;
- representing political, socio-economic and cultural interests of communities at the central level;
- combination of administrative and territorial reform and ensuring the integrity of the state;
- implementation of land, budget and other reforms, taking into account national and local interests;
- updating of the human resources potential, the administrative elite through the reform of the civil service and the service in local self-government bodies, etc. [10].

The Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of April 1, 2014 No. 333-p "On Approving the Concept of Reforming Local Self-Government and Territorial Organization of Government in Ukraine" [12] defines the following tasks of reform implementation:

- ensuring the accessibility and quality of public services;
- achieving optimal distribution of powers between local self-government bodies and executive authorities;

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- defining a sound territorial basis for the activities of local self-government bodies and executive authorities in order to ensure the accessibility and proper quality of public services provided by such bodies;
- Creation of adequate material, financial and organizational conditions to ensure the implementation of local and local authorities' own and delegated powers.

Decentralization, therefore, is the transfer of powers and budgetary revenues from governmental bodies to local governments.

The author has come to the conclusion that, despite the multidimensionality of the concept of decentralization, the breadth of classification of its types, forms, models, the essence and content of this process should, above all, invest two main aspects. First, the separation of powers and responsibilities between central, regional and local government, and second, the empowerment of citizens to address political, economic and social problems.

The implementation of decentralization phenomena in the system of state management of social development of regions should be carried out in four main directions: improvement of the organizational structure of state management of social development of regions; identifying and differentiating the functions and powers of all management entities; modernization of the social services sector; improvement of financial mechanisms of realization of tasks of ensuring social development of territories.

An important factor in this process is the clearly defined choice of type of decentralization. It is important not only to state the course of “radical decentralization of power” chosen by Ukraine as one of the conditions for modernization and optimization of territorial and administrative bases of public services provision to the public, but also to specify the type / model of decentralization at the constitutional and legislative levels.

Moreover, given the European integration course of proclaimed reforms, European understanding of the essence of decentralization is of particular importance. Therefore, further studies need to examine the experience of European countries in implementing decentralization of power and the mechanisms of decentralization of governance tested by foreign systems in the context of their implementation in national practice of public administration.

Analyzing the international experience of decentralization, we observe tendencies to increase the efficiency of self-government, which requires an optimal model of the administrative-territorial structure of the state. Therefore, reforms are taking place not only in post-socialist countries, such as Poland, but also in advanced European democracies, in particular, France and Sweden. Reforming the administrative and territorial system in the states of Europe is aimed primarily at enhancing the basic level of the administrative and territorial system - the community.

Analyzing the basic approaches to decentralization, the author made the following conclusions: the state can carry out decentralization of power in the interests of the population, on the basis of law, transferring part of the powers of executive bodies to local self-government bodies; decentralization of powers must take into account the principle of subsidiarity, ie in such a way as to delegate powers to the level of government closest to the citizen, which is able to fulfill this authority more effectively than other bodies; by transferring powers from the executive or local self-government bodies to a higher level of territorial structure to a lower level, the necessary resources should be transferred and the right of the local self-government authority should be allowed to decide on the delegated powers based on local peculiarities.

Summarizing the initial stage of decentralization of power, one can point to a number of strategic and tactical defects in the current model of self-government reform in Ukraine. The strategic plan remains unclear in terms of achieving the following priorities: "de-oligarchization" of regional development and ensuring territorial integrity in the face of external threats and risks of increasing centrifugal trends at the central and regional levels. Tactically, we can point to a lack of effort to support and encourage self-governing reform. These problems include: limitations of authority and unclear division of functions between the center and regions, uncertainty of the scope of responsibilities and responsibilities of local state administrations; high level of budgetary and financial dependence of local budgets on the center; unresolved issues related to land management, land registration at the local level, etc; obsolete administrative and territorial structure in Ukraine, which does not meet the requirements of time and current challenges.

In general, it should be noted that the years 2015-2018 have been effective and successful in the context of decentralization, since the creation of territorial communities through a mechanism of voluntary association, the transfer of significant powers and financial resources from public authorities to local governments - are perhaps the main principles of reform decentralization in Ukraine. In total, during the active phase of the decentralization reform, 850 organized territorial communities with 8,551,692 residents were created.

It should be noted that during 2014-2018 a number of laws were enacted to create an adequate legal framework for effective decentralization of power, as well as for enhancing the ability of local governments to represent the interests of territorial communities. Such laws were: “the Law on the Cooperation of Territorial Communities”, “the Law on the Principles of State Regional Policy”, “the Law on the Voluntary

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Association of Territorial Communities”, “the Law on Amendments to the Budget Code of Ukraine on Intergovernmental Relations Reform”, and “on the Introduction amendments to the Tax Code of Ukraine and some legislative acts of Ukraine on tax reform”, “On military-civil administrations”.

A special place in the system of legal regulation of the decentralization reform is the Sustainable Development Strategy "Ukraine 2020". It is stated in this document that the main purpose of decentralization policy is to move away from the centralized model of government in the country, to ensure the capacity of local self-government and to build an effective system of territorial organization of power in Ukraine, to fully implement the provisions of the European Charter of Local Self-Government, the principles of subsidiarity and financial self-sufficiency of local self-government.

It is worth noting, in order to accelerate the decentralization processes, on December 6, 2018, the President of Ukraine signed the Decree “On additional measures to ensure the reforms on decentralization of power”. As a consequence of the issued Decree, in the near future a bill on improving the legislation on local elections in connection with the formation of united territorial communities should be submitted to the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine; measures have been developed to provide state support for the completion and formation of capable territorial communities throughout Ukraine by 2020; a plan of measures was developed to strengthen the capacity of local communities, as well as to promote the development of rural areas, in particular by increasing the volume of financial support to local governments.

We consider it necessary to emphasize the process of budgetary decentralization. The author concludes that the amendments to the Tax and Budget Codes have significantly increased the financial capacity of local governments, and in the future allow to make economically self-sufficient and capable new united communities.

The united communities have received the full range of powers and financial resources that are currently held by regional cities, including 60% of PITs allocated for their own powers, direct intergovernmental relations with the state budget, state subsidies.

Since 2015, local budget replenishment sources have been expanded by transferring from the state budget to a range of taxes, as well as introducing new fees. In particular, the local government now collects 100% of the administration fees, 100% of the state duty, 10% of the corporate income tax. However, local budgets receive fees for retail sales of excise goods (beer, alcohol, tobacco, petroleum products) at a rate of 5% of the value of goods sold. In addition, their income is replenished with real estate tax, which is now taxed on commercial (non-residential) property, with a large engine car tax, 80% environmental tax (instead of 35%) and 25% of subsoil payments.

It is important to emphasize that the implementation of decentralization reform in Ukraine has several stages. The first stage involved the transfer of part of the state's powers to the lowest administrative-territorial level - to newly created united territorial communities. The first stage of reform is aimed at reorganizing village councils into united territorial communities and eliminating areas. The second stage of the reform involves the formation of the second level of the administrative and territorial structure of the country – areas that will be much larger than now. The beginning of the third stage will mean amending the Constitution of Ukraine. The purpose of the proposed changes is to streamline local governments and the executive power, to build an effective system of territorial organization of government in Ukraine. Viewing the number of regions is not expected. Accordingly, it is significant that multilevel territorial governance in general can be considered as an activity carried out by public administration and non-governmental structures at all levels in relation to a certain territory with the purpose of securing the rights and freedoms of its citizens, organizing the production, location and development of productive forces, harmonization of different interest groups, ensuring socio-economic development, etc.

It should be noted that the new proposed project of administrative-territorial reform is based on the common theory of local self-government and provides for deep decentralization of public administration. In particular, the draft Law “On the Territorial Structure of Ukraine” proposes to liquidate district state administrations and to leave oversight functions for regional state administrations. Instead, it should give the executive committees of the local councils the authority to manage the territories.

The argument "for" decentralization of governance is the improvement of quality of public services and their approximation to the consumer, as well as the example of developed decentralized states. Indeed, the global experience of regional governance is in favor of a decentralized model of territorial development, at which the maximum of authority in this area is transferred to local authorities, in particular local governments.

Summarizing, the recognition of the need to increase the political and legal activity of civil society institutions, in particular territorial communities, assistance from, first of all, state authorities to their involvement and direct involvement in the process of solving local, and as a consequence, regional importance, is dictated by time, world experience, political maturity of Ukrainian society and Ukraine's international commitments.

Therefore, the search for effective ways to ensure the financial capacity of the united territorial communities should be based on the realization of their own financial potential and diversification of local

budget revenues. This is seen as a prerequisite for sustainable socio-economic development of territorial communities and the implementation in Ukraine of local government reform and territorial organization of government.

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